

Viscosity of Aqueous Electrolyte Solutions as a Function of B Coefficients

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The dependence of viscosity on the strength of electrolyte solutions at high concentrations has been correlated with the B coefficients of the electrolytes. A general polynomial form of equation has been proposed and tested on the available experimental data at different temperatures. Restricted forms of this polynomial equation are necessary to account for the viscosities in the 0.1M-1M, and > 1M concentration ranges. Unreported B coefficients for some electrolytes and separate ions have been evaluated for different temperatures.

THE solvent structure modification property of electrolytes is well known through their viscosity B coefficients¹. For dilute solutions (< 0.1M), the viscosity of electrolyte solution is given by the equation of Jones and Dole²,

$$\eta_r = 1 + BC \quad (1)$$

where η_r is the relative viscosity and C is the concentration. The viscosity equation of Einstein³, meant for dilute solutions of spherical suspensions, is identical with equation (1) for $B = 2.5\bar{V}$.

$$\eta_r = 1 + 2.5\bar{V}C \quad (2)$$

where \bar{V} is the effective rigid molar volume of the electrolyte.

Equations (1) and (2) do not hold for concentrated solutions ($C > 0.1M$), and various equations have been put forward⁴⁻⁷. The validity of these equations has been compared in a recent paper⁸. It has been observed that the equations of Vand⁴, Thomas⁵ and Moulik⁶ hold only in a limited manner. This makes scope for further study in this area. An attempt has been made by Breslau and Miller⁹ through the B coefficients of electrolytes on the rigid assumption that the equation of Thomas⁵ holds for all the electrolytes. The non generality of this approach has been indicated⁸.

In this paper an attempt has been made to correlate the viscosity of concentrated electrolyte solutions through the B coefficients in a different manner.

Equations

The viscosity of a solution can be expressed by a polynomial equation of the type

$$\eta_r = 1 + k_1\phi + k_2\phi^2 + k_3\phi^3 + \dots \quad (3)$$

where the volume fraction of the solute (electrolyte), $\phi = \bar{V}C$. In this relation \bar{V} has been taken to be non variant^{8, 8-11}. For polymer solutions, Thomas⁵ empirically found that the terms higher than ϕ^3 can be neglected and the constants k_1 and k_2 are 2.5 and 10.05 respectively.

Then for $B = 2.5\bar{V}$,

$$\eta_r = 1 + BC + 1.608 B^2C^2 \quad (4)$$

The term 1.608 is required to multiply with B^2 to yield k_2 (10.05) for polymer solutions. This may not be so for electrolytes. It has been already shown⁸ that whenever applicable, the k_2 term of Thomas equation is seldom 10.05 for concentrated electrolyte solutions.

The simplified attempt of Breslau and Miller⁹ to calculate \bar{V} , using Thomas equation without testing its validity separately, gave them some unusual results. The relation $B = 2.5\bar{V}$ was, therefore, revealed not to be so (interestingly the basic equation (4) contains this idea in its second term).

With the assumptions, (1) that the relation $B = 2.5\bar{V}$ holds for electrolytes⁸, and (2) that the polynomial equation (3) holds for them, we can write

$$\eta_r = 1 + BC + (B^2)^nC^2 + (B^3)^mC^3 + \dots \quad (5)$$

where n and m are constants.

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Now neglecting the C^3 and higher terms and also assuming that the square terms in C may or may not be sufficient always, we may further write

$$\eta_r = 1 + BC + (B^2)^n C^{(1+l)} \quad (6)$$

where l is a constant whose values are restricted within the limits $1 \leq l \leq 2$.

On rearrangement we get,

$$\left\{ \frac{(\eta_r - 1)}{C} - B \right\} = (B^2)^n C^l \quad (7)$$

or,

$$\log \left\{ \frac{(\eta_r - 1)}{C} - B \right\} = 2n \log B + l \log C \quad (8)$$

Equation (8) can be directly tested with the experimental viscosity data, and if holds, the values of n and l can be ascertained.

Results

The experimental viscosity values obtained from various sources and quoted in the International Encyclopedia of Physical Chemistry and Chemical Physics¹⁰ have been processed to test equation (8). The B coefficients are always needed for this. Such values at 25° for a good number of electrolytes are found in the literature⁹. The values at other temperatures are not that common. These have been evaluated either by the graphical interpolation method of the available B values or by using the viscosity equation of Vand⁴. The second procedure is permissible because Vand's equation holds for many electrolytes at different temperatures. This has been tested: the results are not shown for saving space. In Table 1 various B values for several electrolytes at different temperatures are listed. The ionic B coefficients obtained from these electrolytes are given in Table 2.

In Figure 1, the validity of Thomas equation (4) has been presented. It is seen that the fitting is poor; deviations are pronounced at higher concentrations. Significantly improved fittings of these viscosity data with equation (8) are exemplified in Figure 2. The importance of this equation lies in its independency on temperature and the nature of the electrolytes. In Table 3, the constant terms n and l as evaluated from the plots are listed. Making allowances for the experimental errors, and rounding off the values, the term n emerges to be very close to unity in all the cases. As was anticipated, the term l is sometimes 1 and sometimes greater than 1 (1.5 in many instances).

Now considering that the parent polynomial equation (3) holds (equation (8) is the restricted form of equation (5)), estimation of viscosity values from the B coefficients may be possible. We now write,

$$\eta_r = 1 + BC + (B^2)^n C^2 + (B^3)^m C^3 \quad (9)$$

TABLE 1— B COEFFICIENTS OF SALTS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Salt	Temp. ($^\circ$ C)	B
AgBr ^a	25	0.059
AgNO ₃ ^b	25	0.045
CuSO ₄ ^b	25	0.594
	30	0.403
	40	0.360
	50	0.338
	60	0.292
KCl ^b	30	0.0084
	40	0.0163
	50	0.0332
	55	0.0365
KF ^b	25	0.113
KI ^a	25	-0.076
LiNO ₃ ^b	25	0.104
NaBr ^b	25	0.054
	30	0.084
NaCl ^a	25	0.080
	30	0.086
	40	0.096
	50	0.104
	55	0.106
NaI ^a	25	0.018
NaNO ₃ ^b	30	0.054
	40	0.075
	50	0.090
	55	0.098
Na ₂ SO ₄ ^a	25	0.381
	30	0.388
	40	0.409
	50	0.426
	60	0.444
NiSO ₄ ^b	30	0.565
	40	0.502
	50	0.442
	60	0.380
ZnSO ₄ ^b	30	0.435
	40	0.392
	50	0.372
	60	0.325

^a B from graphical interpolation.

^b B from vand's equation.

Now n has been shown equal to 1. Taking $n = m$ Discussion = 1,

$$\eta_r = 1 + BC + B^2C^2 + B^3C^3 \quad (10)$$

Fig. 1. Test of Thomas equation for some electrolytes
 1 : NaNO_3 (30°); 2 : AgNO_3 (25°); 3 : NaBr (25°);
 4 : KF (25°); 5 : LiNO_3 (25°); 6 : NiSO_4 (60°);
 7 : ZnSO_4 (60°); 8 : Na_2SO_4 (27°); 9 : CaNO_3 (30°).
 CuSO_4 , ZnSO_4 , NiSO_4 , Na_2SO_4 —Scale II.

So far as we know the B values, listed in Table 1, for temperatures other than 25° are not given in the literature. These are seen to be less in magnitude with increasing temperature in some cases, and *vice versa*. This is because ions constituting the electrolytes do show either decrease or increase in their individual B values with change of temperature (Table 2). The individual ionic B values have been obtained on separation basis taking the ionic B values of K^+ and Cl^- to be equal at all temperatures. The available B values of the other ions were also utilized to compute the ionic values of a salt. One exception to this is Na^+ , whose B values are the same for all the temperatures. It is usually known and accepted that both K^+ and Cl^- ions have equal B values¹. In our attempt to calculate the B values of K^+ by subtracting the interpolated Cl^- values from the coefficient of KCl found from the equation of Vand, there occurred differences in magnitude between K^+ and Cl^- (see Table 2). This may be attributed to the errors incurred in the experiments, and graphical evaluations of B from the Jones-Dole and Vand equations, if not allowed to the uncertainty of the so far accepted concept of equal B values of both K^+ and Cl^- at all temperatures.

Fig. 2. Test of equation 8 for some electrolytes
 1 : KCl (55°); 2 : NaNO_3 (55°); 3 : AgNO_3 (25°); 4 : NaBr (50°); 5 : LiNO_3 (25°); 6 : NaBr (25°);
 7 : NiSO_4 and ZnSO_4 (60°).

However, other forms are also considered.

$$\eta_r = 1 + BC + B^2C^{2.5} \quad (11)$$

$$\eta_r = 1 + BC + B^2C^2 \quad (12)$$

Calculation of relative viscosities using equations (10)–(12) has been made for many electrolytes. The results indicate that for high B values equation (10) calculates a viscosity very close to the observed figure, so long the concentration is close to 1M. Beyond this concentration limit equations (11) and (12) fit the results better. (These results are involved with the uncertainties of both B and η_r , which are only experimental quantities).

The viscosity-concentration equations now proposed are accepted for (1) they contain no ambiguous constant terms, and (2) they may be used with the so far acknowledged viscosity equations suggested for concentrated solutions. However, the unavailability of enough B values for various temperatures restricted the verification of the equations in many instances. Whenever possible this solvent structure modifying parameter has been worked out applying the equation of VK and, but for only those electrolytes for which the latter is valid.⁸

The present study signifies that we have now equations at our disposal which can cover results from moderate to high concentrations. In addition

TABLE 2—IONIC B COEFFICIENTS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Ions	$B_{c,d}$ Temperature(°C)					
	25	30	40	50	55	60
Ag ⁺	0.091	—	—	—	—	—
Br ⁻	-0.032	—	—	0.004	—	—
Cl ⁻	-0.007	-0.0004	0.0098	0.018	0.0198	—
Cu ⁺⁺	0.385	0.199	0.135	0.106	—	0.053
K ⁺	-0.007	-0.008	0.0065	0.0157	0.067	—
Na ⁺	0.086	0.086	0.086	0.086	0.086	0.086
Ni ⁺⁺	0.384	0.349	0.265	0.188	—	0.108
NO ₃ ⁻	-0.046	-0.033	-0.011	0.004	0.011	—
SO ₄ ⁻⁻	0.209	0.216	0.237	0.254	—	0.272
Zn ⁺⁺	0.370	0.266	0.180	0.158	—	0.080

c: literature values for I⁻ at 25° and 35° are -0.0685 and -0.0536 respectively.

d: some comments on the K⁺ values are given in the discussion section.

TABLE 3— n , l AND B VALUES FOR SOME ELECTROLYTES^e

Salt	Temp.(°C)	n	l	B
AgNO ₃	25	0.63	1	0.045
CuSO ₄	30	1	1.5	0.403
	40	1	1.5	0.360
	60	1	1.5	0.292
KCl	30	1	1.5	0.0084
	55	1	1.5	0.0365
KF	25	1	1	0.113
LaCl ₃	25	1	1	0.567
LiCl	25	1	1	0.140
LiNO ₃	25	1	1.5	0.1034
NaBr	25	1	1.5	0.054
	50	1	1.5	0.082
NaCl	35	1	1	0.090
	50	1	1	0.104
NaNO ₃	30	1	1.5	0.0535
	55	1	1	0.0975
Na ₂ SO ₄	25	1	1	0.381
	27	1	1	0.384
	34	1	1	0.397
NiSO ₄	40	1.3	1	0.502
	60	1.3	1	0.380
ZnSO ₄	30	1	2	0.435
	60	1	1.5	0.325

e: the viscosity data of Janz *et al.*¹¹ at 25° on similar treatments result B values of 0.08, 0.06 and 0.064 for the salt NaCl, NaClO₄ and NaCNS respectively; B values of -0.026 and 0.022 for the ions ClO₄⁻ and CNS⁻, respectively; n and l values of 0.82 and 1.0 for NaCl, 1.06 and 2.45 for NaClO₄, and 0.98 and 1.06 for NaCNS respectively.

to the Jones-Dole equation (valid for $C \leq 0.1M$), equation (10) (working limit $0.1M \leq C \leq 1M$), and equations (11) and (12) (valid for $C > 1M$) are all members of one type of polynomial equation. The results given in Table 3 show only a minor exception to this (AgNO₃ and NiSO₄). In a recent paper, Janz *et al.*¹² have reported various forms of viscosity equations containing C², C³ and C⁴ terms and some arbitrary constants, for concentrated solutions of NaCl, NaNO₃, NaClO₄ and NaCNS.

The equation of Thomas (which is a special case of the polynomial equation (3)) in terms of the B coefficients is not easily conceived when applied to polymer solutions, since the concept of B coefficient for polymers is not clear. The results reported in this paper further support that Thomas equation applied to the electrolyte solutions may not be adequate and sufficient. The K_s terms of the modified Thomas equation⁸ may be correlated with B coefficients which is a specific property of an electrolyte.

The proposed equations have been found to be true at all temperatures between 25°–60°. Experimental viscosity values at other temperatures are but very scarce, and the B values are not known. Further experiments are, therefore, necessary for an elaborate understanding of the present proposition.

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